

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2022 Annual Progress Report

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Executive Summary

What is the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program and why is it needed?

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is funded by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) and led by a team of scientists from six Ohio universities through the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN). Its mission is to independently assess the ability of wetland restoration Projects to reduce nutrients and improve water quality. The information gained will allow Ohio to demonstrate where widespread wetland restoration is a sound investment and to improve the design and management of restored wetlands.

The ODNR restores wetlands using the best available information, but there are still gaps in scientific understanding. Wetland ecosystems have been called “the kidneys of the landscape” because of their ability to filter pollutants and improve water quality. No two wetlands are identical, and although wetlands are often effective water filters, their capacity to prevent excess nutrients from moving downstream varies. For example, wetlands restored on human-altered landscapes are particularly vulnerable to nutrient release because of the accumulation of legacy phosphorus.

What has the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program achieved so far?

- Created a novel and comprehensive monitoring framework that was evaluated and codified by scientific and management advisory committees.
- Implemented monitoring of all completed ODNR restoration Projects.
- Leveraged the State’s investment to obtain a \$3 million federal award from the US EPA’s Great Lakes Restoration Initiative for expanding data collection and synthesis.
- Developed centralized data management and quality control systems to ensure credibility, accessibility, and accountability.
- Established partnerships with landowners and conservation organizations to incorporate their knowledge into monitoring efforts.
- Engaged community members to better understand and value the wetlands being built in their backyards and across the state.

What will the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program accomplish with continued support?

Long-term funding will support the ODNR’s commitment to clean and accessible water across Ohio. The H2Ohio wetland restoration Projects and the Monitoring Program build upon Ohio’s rich history of science based natural resource management. Through a university driven program, the ODNR is investing in Ohio’s workforce through student and early career training. Further, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program is leading in its field as it generates transferable monitoring approaches. Wetland ecosystems are dynamic, and no single year will demonstrate or predict future success in nutrient load reduction. Early measurements may suggest restoration trajectories and after multiple years, certainty in assessments will improve.

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Program Overview

The Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR) contracted the Wetlands and Water Quality Research Group within the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN) to develop and implement the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program (hereafter Wetland Monitoring Program, WMP, or Monitoring Program). The goal of the Monitoring Program is to assess the nutrient removal function of wetland restoration and enhancement Projects implemented by the ODNR as part of Governor Mike DeWine’s statewide [H2Ohio Initiative](#). The Wetland Monitoring Program focuses on phosphorus and nitrogen, key nutrients that fuel eutrophication and harmful algal blooms across Ohio. Core questions that focus the Monitoring Program include:

- Which types of wetland structure and function provide enhanced nutrient reduction and retention?
- Which wetland restoration approaches maximize cost-effectiveness to mitigate nutrient loads to Ohio water bodies?
- How can wetland restoration be effectively implemented in the future?

Figure 1. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Development Timeline (top) and the cumulative total of ODNR-implemented H2Ohio Initiative wetland restoration Projects under contract (bottom) each year starting in 2019.

The present document is the first annual report since the inception of the Wetland Monitoring Program in 2020 (Figure 1). [The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Monitoring Plan \(2021\)](#) was completed by the LEARN Wetlands and Water Quality Research Group and approved by the ODNR in June 2021 after review by a 26-member Technical Advisory Panel and a five-member Management Advisory Panel. The Plan details the methods and frameworks utilized by the Program. While some preliminary data was collected in 2021, many protocols and policies were in development, including clarification of roles of ODNR and LEARN in cooperative workflows (Appendix, Figure A1). Thus, efforts in 2021 were dedicated to 1) characterizing completed restoration Projects to design monitoring and 2) hiring and training technical staff and students across the 11 data collection crews at six Ohio universities. In 2022, the Wetland Monitoring Program continued to grow capacity and completed collection of the first year of baseline data from 45 wetland restoration Projects as of October 1, 2022 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. 2022 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Year-In-Review. Quantitative overview of data collection and capacity building accomplished in 2022 by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program, funded by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources and implemented by university researchers from the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network.

Program Structure

Monitoring Phases

For each monitored H2Ohio wetland Project, *Project Characterization* is pre- or post-construction sampling related to preliminary understanding of a Project (Appendix, Figure A1). Researchers assess major site features and flow paths to inform sampling. Information gathered during the Project Characterization monitoring phase is documented in and used to develop a Project Specific Monitoring Plan. *Routine Monitoring* is post-construction and post-characterization sampling at standard locations across a wetland Project.

Tiered Approach: Focal and Non-Focal Projects

To balance broad state-wide assessment with understanding function to inform management, the Wetland Monitoring Program uses a tiered sampling approach. In 2022, the Program selected six Focal Projects for intensive monitoring from 45 wetland Projects (Appendix, Table A1) that represented major "types" of wetland restoration approaches and logistical considerations (Table 1, Figure A2). Focal Projects are prioritized for specialized data collection and sampled at a greater frequency and higher resolution than Non-Focal Projects.

Table 1. 2022 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Focal Projects. Wetland restoration projects implemented by the ODNR through the H2Ohio Water Quality Initiative selected for intensive, high frequency monitoring in 2022 by the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Six Focal Projects were selected from 45 wetland Projects that represented major "types" of wetland restoration approaches and logistical considerations.

Focal Project	Wetland Restoration Approach and Logistical Considerations
St. Joseph River Restoration Forder Bridge Oakwoods East Oakwoods West	Common floodplain and inland depressional wetland restoration approaches used in the agricultural Western Lake Erie Basin. Comprehensive documentation of site history and strong relationships with grant recipients facilitated effective planning for early years of monitoring and beyond.
Magee Marsh	Diked coastal wetland reconnection with active water level management. Convenient location for the UT-based lead sensor technician to pilot a real-time telemetric sensor network.
Brooks Park	Flow-through treatment train typical of many Ohio River Basin Projects. Relatively easily defined features, but with bi-directional flow. The relatively small area (five acres) makes it logistically feasible to comprehensively characterize soil processes along flow paths.

Data Collection Crews

The Program consists of researchers from Bowling Green State University (BGSU), University of Toledo (UT), Heidelberg University (HU), Wright State University (WSU), and Kent State University (KSU) that facilitate two types of data collection crews.

Regional Base Crews

- Monitor Projects assigned by geography (Figure 3). Base crews are broken down into Northwest Inland (BGSU), Northwest Coastal (UT), Northcentral (HU), Southwest and Central (WSU), and Northeast (KSU).
- Responsible for planning and implementing general soil and water sampling and chemical analyses of soil and water samples.
- Consist of one or two faculty Principal Investigator (PI), at least one full-time field and lab staff, and multiple part-time technicians, typically graduate and undergraduate students.

Specialty Crews

- Plan and implement sampling with specialized expertise, tools, and equipment.
- Include Aerial Imagery (Drone, UT), Vegetation (BGSU), Hydrogeophysics (UT), Automated Sensors (UT), Hydrodynamic Modeling (BGSU), and Sediment-scale Measurements (KSU, WSU).
- Generally, they have a similar staffing structure to Base Crews (i.e., PI, field staff, student technicians).

Figure 3. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Regional Base Crews. Map illustrating how Ohio Department of Natural Resources implemented H2Ohio wetland Projects under contract as of December 2022 are distributed among five geographically delineated Base Crews (indicated by color) and run by members of the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Base Crews are responsible for planning and implementing routine monitoring at H2Ohio Projects within their region. Larger circled points indicate Projects that were sampled by Base Crews in 2022.

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 2022 Progress

This section describes progress made in 2022 toward answering the core Wetland Monitoring Program questions. Successes grew from early investment in data management infrastructure, documentation workflows, well-trained full-time staff, and partnerships with end users.

Which types of wetland structure and function provide enhanced nutrient reduction and retention?

Data collection

H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Researchers visited, gathered information about restoration approaches used at, and collected data reflecting nutrient function in 45 H2Ohio wetland Projects in 2022 (Table 2, Table A1). The intensity and resolution of data collection varied across projects based on a tiered approach. To inform data collection decisions based on features specific to unique restoration projects, the Program implemented standardized Project

Specific Monitoring Plan templates to be used for each routinely monitored project. For more details regarding data collection, please see Regional Base Crew Highlights and Specialty Crew Highlights. A comprehensive list of Project attributes including hydrologic structure (i.e., broad assessment of main wetland hydrology type), land holder type, county, Project acres, and completion year are included in Appendix, Table A2.

Table 2. 2022 Wetland Monitoring Program Data Collection Overview. Measurements collected at Ohio Department of Natural Resources-implemented H2Ohio wetland Projects by the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program in 2022.

Data	Number of Projects	Measurements
Water and Soil	44	>1,300 water samples > 600 soil samples
Vegetation	11	>800 plant biomass samples
Drone Imagery	11	Aerial imagery across 14 drone flights
Geophysical	6	>80 km of geophysical measurement transects
Sediment-Scale	3	48 intact sediment-surface water nutrient exchange cores
Sensor Systems	1	Meteorological data at 5-minute sampling interval across two months (November and December 2022)
		Physicochemical data at 10-minute sampling interval across two months (October and November 2022) from 4 sensor stations
	5	~ 1 year of continuous (15-minute sampling interval) physicochemical measurements with eight YSI sondes

Quality control and quality assurance

To align with environmental monitoring data management best practices, custom-built electronic forms were implemented using Esri ArcGIS Survey123 (“surveys”) and a standardized sample identification system for water, soil, and vegetation samples. These sample identifiers and electronic surveys automatically track critical metadata associated with each field sampling event including time, date, location, and conditions at each collected sample (Table 2). Semi-automated data quality control systems to screen data for common errors were created and implemented. For more details, please see Data Management Infrastructure. A program-wide quality assurance plan is currently under development to compile and standardize quality assurance procedures and acceptance criteria currently used by individual data collection Crews.

Project Specific Monitoring Plans

Early Project Specific Monitoring Plan templates were improved in 2022 by explicitly including hydrologic structural categorization. General hydrologic structure was identified as a primary wetland attribute important to nutrient function by researchers in [The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Monitoring Plan \(2021\)](#). 19 completed Projects were characterized before routine monitoring began in 2022. Primary wetland hydrologic types of routinely monitored Projects in 2022 included eight complexes (mix of hydrologic types), four inland depressional wetlands, three coastal wetlands, two flow-through wetlands, one inland depressional wetland and one unknown (due to limited site access). Further, the diversity of hydrologic management is

evident with water level control structures at seven Projects and tile drainage influence at five Projects (Appendix, Table A2).

Science Driven Decision Making

In 2022, the Program continued to grow a “toolbox” of approaches to design appropriate monitoring for diverse wetland structures and conditions. Insights from researchers’ expertise in river, lake, and wetland science inform Program-wide policies and Project-specific decisions regarding sampling frequency, spatial extent, and monitoring activities. Two approaches that WMP researchers developed further in 2022 include integrating storm sampling to consider the full hydrograph (i.e., different parts of the storm flow from ambient to peak flow), as well as considering water residence time and watershed weighted techniques to guide sampling.

Three Working Groups, small groups of Program researchers and external researchers, met quarterly in 2022. The Nutrient Budgeting Working Group focused on how best to estimate nutrient budgets, which is a key synthesis concept for the Program’s diverse datasets; they drafted conceptual nutrient budget diagrams for different types of wetlands. A Data Analysis Group focused on methods for program-level data analysis; they identified wetland attributes relevant to nutrient function. A third Working Group refined water level monitoring across Projects by selecting water level measurement tools (e.g., staff gauges and digital water level logging sensors) and determining optimal locations within Projects for water level monitoring.

Leveraged Support

The Monitoring Program obtained a \$3 million grant from the US EPA Great Lakes Restoration Initiative and \$250,000 in funding from Ohio Department of Higher Education (ODHE) Harmful Algal Bloom Research Initiative (HABRI) to enhance researchers’ capacity to not only directly assess individual wetlands, but to synthesize nutrient reduction/water quality benefits across different wetland types and geographies. Please see Leveraging Monitoring Efforts to Build Capacity for details.

Which wetland restoration approaches maximize cost-effectiveness to mitigate nutrient loads to Ohio water bodies?

Integrating Management Perspectives

Researchers developed relationships with over 60 wetland managers, property owners, and other partners in 2022. The January 2022 Annual Workshop (held virtually) brought together 34 Program researchers and 18 partners (i.e., ODNr managers, Project collaborators, external researchers) from 15 different institutions to update the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Plan, review 2021 activities and progress, and plan for 2022. Through informal communication and formal data collection tools developed in 2022, researchers track management decisions and actions to support assessing the management action impacts. For example, in select Projects with water level control infrastructure, managers log water level management events using a custom-built smart phone survey that was built and implemented in 2022. Researchers can thus incorporate knowledge of water release events, which may contribute to the wetland’s net

nutrient budget, into Project assessments, which will ultimately inform future management decisions.

Improved Communication

Among researchers within the Monitoring Program, improved workflows in 2022 enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of information exchange and data compilation across institutions. Monitoring Program and ODNR staff communication was also improved through monthly restoration Project status updates and by establishing a standard place to share documents that detail costs and other features of restoration approaches. Lastly, the Program remained committed to communicating its progress to the public with an annual webinar hosted by Ohio Sea Grant and LEARN on October 12, 2022. In conjunction with the public webinar, the Program created a two-page overview [brochure](#) for general audiences.

How can wetland restoration be effectively implemented in the future?

Foundation For Long Term Monitoring

In 2022, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program continued to implement policies, establish infrastructure, and cultivate relationships to sustain monitoring in the long term, which is necessary for reliable wetland restoration assessment and planning. Standardized data collection, a science-based framework, and concurrent interactions among researchers, agency Project leaders, and land managers have been established for a Program-wide synthesis of Project level data across multiple years of data collection. From the first years of measurements, results may provide indicators of wetland restoration success that can inform management decisions. After many years of repeated measurements, a more comprehensive and accurate ecological assessment of wetlands restored for nutrient reduction goals can be achieved.

Regional Base Crew Highlights

Base Crews visited 45 H2Ohio wetland Projects for Project Characterization and/or Routine Monitoring sampling in 2022 (Figure 3, Table A1). Crews collected more comprehensive data in 2022 than in 2021 due to increased staff and consistent planning documents. Collectively, the Program onboarded six new full-time employees to increase planning, sampling, and analysis capacity (Appendix, Table A3). Sample processing, lab analyses, quality assurance and quality control procedures to validate data collected in 2022 will continue into 2023. Datasets remain provisional for at least one year after collection to ensure adequate quality control, which is standard in large environmental monitoring programs.

Communication between Base Crew researchers and ODNR managers, Project collaborators, and Project managers in 2022 facilitated site access and monitoring logistics. Partners also helped solve “mysteries” about site attributes, such as tile drain outlets and other cryptic inflows or outflows. The relative roles of Project collaborators (grantee and contractors) and Project site managers (longer-term site contacts) in informing wetland researchers varies by Project.

Base Crew researchers noted logistical and sampling challenges. Some challenges were overcome with intentional efforts to enhance coordination among Base and Specialty Crews (e.g., sharing equipment and Project contact lists) and others are beyond the Program’s control

(e.g., entry road conditions, unexpected site disturbances). Low water levels were experienced across many wetland Projects due to low precipitation in the summer of 2022, leading to enhanced efforts at capturing transient storm and flood events for water sampling. At times, there were limited connections between the restored wetland and surrounding watershed, which is a valuable preliminary observation that underscores the importance of multi-year datasets to track restored wetland function.

Project Specific Monitoring Plans document monitoring design and data collection decisions. Although formally updated annually, Project Specific Monitoring Plans function as living documents to support adaptive monitoring. Program review of 2022 Plans identified where sampling design can be further standardized across the Program and where continued flexibility is needed (Table 3).

Table 3. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Adaptive Changes. Examples of the H2Ohio’s WMP “Learning by Doing in an Adaptive Framework,” as identified during creation of 2022 Project Specific Monitoring Plans.

Furthering standardization	2022: identified that Crews had different relative proportions of ambient (base flow) versus event-based (most often storm flow) sampling frequency.	2023: efforts to be made to define a Program-wide rubric for sampling frequency for different hydrologic types and monitoring intensities (Focal versus Non-Focal).
Documenting flexibility	Notable size differences and site access nuances across wetland Projects led to unique sampling schemes across wetland types and restoration approaches. Examples: Each small wetland pool is sampled at Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West and manual post-storm event sampling is relatively easy. In contrast, at Magee Marsh inflow, outflow, water level control structures are sampled but site limitations post-storms make automated samplers beneficial.	

The following highlights for each geographic Base Crew illustrate challenges and accomplishments experienced in 2022. For a complete list of water and soil samples collected by Base Crews from each Project, see Appendix, Table A4.

Northwest Inland (Bowling Green State University)

- Sampled 11 Projects (eight Routine Monitoring and three pre-construction characterization), collected 641 water samples and 456 soil samples.
- Trained one full-time technician and nine part-time technicians.
- Collected a high number of samples (~40 samples per Project compared to other Crews ~10 samples per Project) at five out of eight Projects they routinely monitor to characterize complex hydrologic structure types and to design effective sampling plans.

Northwest Coastal (University of Toledo)

- Sampled seven Projects (five Routine Monitoring, one post-construction characterization, one pre-construction characterization), collected 320 water samples and 73 soil samples.

- Trained one full-time technician and four part-time technicians.
- Responded to coastal wetland restoration approaches by creating monitoring sampling designs to adapt to logistical challenges (e.g., large coastal wetland size and open water).

North central (Heidelberg University)

- Sampled nine wetlands (three Routine Monitoring, five post-construction characterization, one pre-construction characterization), collected 76 water samples and 29 soil samples.
- Trained one full-time technician and five part-time technicians.
- Responded to intermittent surface water pooling by installing water level loggers, after anecdotal evidence (field notes from sampling visits) suggested surface water exchange between a creek or river and Project wetland pools may be limited.

Southwest and Central (Wright State University)

- Sampled 16 wetlands (three Routine Monitoring, one post-construction characterization, 12 pre-construction characterization), collected 298 water samples and 91 soil samples.
- Trained one new full-time technician and nine part-time technicians (continued one full-time technician from 2021).
- Responded to unique flow patterns at Focal Project Brooks Park by designing monitoring to account for potential bi-directional flow between Buckeye Lake and the wetland.

Northeast (Kent State University)

- Sampled two Projects (one post-construction characterization, one pre-construction characterization), collected 76 water samples and 29 soil samples.
- Trained four part-time technicians. Only Base Crew without a full-time field lead technician; current sampling efforts being implemented by graduate student who is also co-leading sediment scale measurements.
- No Northeast Ohio H2Ohio Wetland Projects were completed in time for full characterization or Routine Monitoring in 2022.

Specialty Crew Highlights

Specialty Crews collected data across 11 H2Ohio Wetland Projects in 2022 to support synthesis and scaling up of Base Crew water and soil samples (Appendix, Table A5). Specialized data collection is often more time-, labor-, and cost-intensive than snapshot water and soil sampling. Thus, specialty crews consistently consider tradeoffs in efficiency, cost, and accuracy. Given the emerging technology and methods utilized by Specialty Crews, significant time was spent on continued onboarding and training of full-time staff to enhance Monitoring Program capacity to conduct necessary data collection tasks that require specialized expertise (Appendix, Table A3). Drone and hydrogeophysics technical staff trained in 2022 have relieved constraints that the Monitoring Program faced in 2021. Likewise in 2022, a Principal Sensor Technician was hired to develop sensor system design best practices, assemble stations, and direct new purchasing. In 2022, Specialty Crews also contributed to capacity building and workforce development through graduate student training and education.

Graduate research projects directly connected to Specialty Crew sampling include:

- Seyi Ogundeji, advised by Richard Becker (University of Toledo), completed the first master thesis that leveraged the Monitoring Program, performing object-based classification of drone imagery to monitor H2Ohio Wetlands.
- Michael Back, advised by Lauren Kinsman-Costello (Kent State University) compares soil core incubation and resin bag deployments for measuring soil nutrient flux.
- Nana-Aboagye Otchere, advised by Kennedy Doro (University of Toledo) examines subsurface water flow variation through Fruth, the first H2Ohio wetland.
- Hannah LaPoint, advised by Kennedy Doro (University of Toledo) assesses how substrate properties impact groundwater and develops methods to image coastal wetland sediments via Electromagnetic Induction and Ground Penetrating Radar at Magee Marsh.
- Ibrahim Mohammed, advised by Ganming Liu and Bob Midden (Bowling Green State University), models hydrologic complexities of wetlands designed for nutrient reduction.

Aerial Imagery (University of Toledo)

The Drone Crew uses unmanned autonomous vehicles to provide high-resolution aerial imagery to characterize wetland Projects and classify vegetation to scale-up nutrient estimates (Figure 4). In 2022, the Crew conducted 13 drone flights and completed orthomosaic (photographic) imagery processing across 11 Projects. The Crew trained one full-time technician. Preliminary imagery-based plant community classification using machine learning techniques was completed for three Projects (Brook Parks, Forder Bridge, St. Joseph Restoration). The Crew addressed the challenges of large-scale data processing and storage by establishing an account at the Ohio Supercomputer. Object-based image analysis for vegetation was switched from Ecognition developer to the opensource Orfell Toolbox package in QGIS primarily to reduce data processing times, with the co-benefit of aligning with the open science goals of the Monitoring Program. With support from the Program's Chief Data Manager, over three Terabytes of processed data were uploaded to the Ohio Supercomputer. Opportunistic drone flights piloted efforts for characterizing wetland basin shape, testing the feasibility of barren ground digital elevation models (DEM) to estimate bathymetry. Preliminary data suggest drone DEMs are neither precise nor accurate enough for specialty hydrological models, but continued testing will assess how DEMs from the Drone Crew can be utilized by other Crews toward Program goals (i.e., assess water flow paths, water volume).

Figure 4. H2Ohio Wetland Project Aerial Imagery. Produced by the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Drone Crew in 2022. Labels indicate Project four letter Project Codes. SRHE = Sandusky River Headwaters, FRUW = Fruth, SJCO = St. Joseph Confluence, SJRE = St. Joseph River Restoration, BWLK = Burntwood Langenkamp, REDB = Redhorse Bend, OAKE/ OAKW = Oakwoods East, Oakwoods West, MAGM = Magee Marsh, FORB = Forder Bridge, BROP = Brooks Park.

Vegetation (Bowling Green State University)

The Vegetation Crew’s data collection tasks aim to assess the role of plants in wetland nutrient uptake and storage by collecting biomass for nutrient content measurements and surveying plant community composition to ground-truth drone imagery and support plant community monitoring with drone imagery (Figure 5). In addition to developing and implementing stratified sampling methods for community composition, the Crew sampled patches of monotypic plants (all one type) to start a training dataset for the segmentation algorithm used by the Drone Crew. The Vegetation Crew uses a unique field collection form developed by the Program’s Chief Data Manager and refined by continued communication with the Vegetation Crew. Such data entry allows for quick initial data processing and quality assurance for community composition measurements. In 2022, the Crew trained 10 part-time technicians (continued two full-time technicians from 2021) and surveyed 446 plots at 11 Projects. Aboveground biomass samples ($n = 562$) were collected and processed (dried and weighed) within a week of collection, after which the Crew began preparing a subset of samples for nutrient analysis. At a subset of Projects (Forder Bridge, Oakwoods East, and Oakwoods West), the Crew collected and processed 238 belowground biomass samples. These Projects were chosen because they represent a range of

species diversity (higher at Forder Bridge and lower at Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West) and were some of the first Projects to have comprehensive Base Crew Sampling (Northwest Base Crew). Likewise, the Crew over-sampled Forder Bridge to quantify effects of sampling intensity on accuracy of summary estimates to inform future sampling plans. Finally, the Crew quantified the time and accuracy tradeoffs of spending more or less time sorting belowground biomass samples, which is important for balancing the efficiency needs of the Monitoring Program with the accuracy needs of a science-based framework.

Figure 5. Vegetation sampling. (A) Example map of Vegetation sampling design at a Forder Bridge (B) Aboveground community composition sampling from bigger plot and biomass sampling from smaller adjacent plot. (C) Belowground biomass sampling from randomly sampled quadrat.

Hydrogeophysics (University of Toledo)

The Hydrogeophysics Crew is tasked with measures and maps the subsurface soil geophysical conditions, which supports, understanding porewater and groundwater flow, building accurate 3-D hydrodynamic models in focal projects for accurate nutrient budgeting, and scaling up discrete point measurements of soil nutrient status and properties. (Figure 6). Geophysical measurements are collectively interpreted to understand patterns of porosity and conductivity in the wetland soil, show stratigraphic layers, and help inform where to place piezometers for measuring subsurface water levels and nutrients. The data collected in 2022 will aid synthesis of Base Crew water and soil water measurements to achieve a more comprehensive assessment of wetland nutrient function. The Crew sampled 10-km of ground-penetrating radar (GPR) transects, 70-km of electromagnetic conductivity (EC) transects, and >1.5-km of electrical resistance tomography (ERT). Soil samples (n= 88) were collected and analyzed for organic matter, moisture, bulk density, pH, porosity across four Projects. Piezometers (n = 10) were installed across four Projects. One non-Focal Project (Fruth) was prioritized for hydrogeophysics sampling because it was an early H2Ohio Wetland Project with complex subsurface interactions that warranted greater investigation (master’s student research).

While initially the Program had planned to utilize hydrogeophysics data to characterize new Projects and make preliminary sampling decisions, a logistical lesson learned this year is there tends to be a lag between when hydrogeophysics data are interpreted and when Base Crews are ready to start monitoring. Moving forward, any new hydrogeophysics data from one year may inform adaptations to monitoring locations in the subsequent year. Another lesson learned was that vegetation and tree plantings may limit all-terrain vehicle access at Project sites. In future geophysical data collection efforts, the Hydrogeophysics Crew will communicate with Project partners to plan data collection so as not to be interfered by restoration plantings. In 2022, the Crew also refined protocols to improve the accuracy of the GPR and EC data. Finally, methods were piloted to take measurements over standing water and correct the conductivity in the surface water.

Figure 6. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Hydrogeophysics Sampling. (A) Electrical conductivity measured via instrument pulled on a sled at Forder Bridge (Efemena Emmanuel and Landan Chapman pictured left to right) (B) Kennedy Doro monitoring electrical resistivity tomography data collection (C) Ground penetrating radar collection with a cart configuration at Fruth (Nana-Aboagye Otchere).

Integrated Sensor Systems (University of Toledo)

The Sensor Crew designs, implements, and maintains integrated sensor systems that autonomously provide high temporal resolution data of water level, physicochemical, and weather data all of which inform general understanding of wetland nutrient function and are used directly in 3-D hydrodynamic models and nutrient budgeting (Figure 7). In 2022, the Crew consisted of a Sensor Infrastructure Specialist who trained with staff at sensor system specialists with the consulting firm LimnoTech (Ann Arbor, MI) and assembled, programmed, and installed the Program’s first sensor system at Magee Marsh. This system consists of a weather and telemetric communication tower (“base station”) measuring wind speed and direction, rainfall, air pressure and solar radiation. Five “sensor stations” collect water temperature, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and turbidity across the wetland. The stations deployed in 2022 contained

sensors loaned by Cleveland Water Alliance, due to order delays of LEARN-purchased equipment. Real-time data went “live” in October 2022. Data from 2022 was uploaded real-time to a web-based dashboard, Ubidots, hosted by LimnoTech. Information collected from the sensors includes meteorological data at 5-minute sampling intervals from November – December 2022 and physiochemistry sensor stations at 10-minute sampling intervals from October – November 2022.

Magee Marsh has been a valuable Project for piloting the Program’s sensor system. The Project’s large size and topography highlighted the need for a larger antenna and optimal tower placement. Lessons learned this year are already being applied in next year’s plans. For example, there is now a list of site characterization criteria for a more efficient sensor system installation process. From a technical perspective, the specific parameters to be measured at each location call for unique sensor pairings that result in different wiring configurations and programming steps. The Sensor Infrastructure Specialist will continue to work closely with the Chief Data Manager to develop workflows for sensor data, with the 3-D Hydrodynamic modeler and Hydrogeophysics Crew to ensure sensors have appropriate accuracies, and with Base Crews to assess site logistics and monitoring needs. While there has been great progress in discerning optimal sensor pairings, an increased number of sites and sensor network complexity (i.e., at St. Joseph Restoration) necessitates considerable time for designing and troubleshooting each custom system. This is a challenge the Program is ready to face in 2023, and one that underscores the need for increased Sensor Specialty Crew staff via leveraged grant funding.

Figure 7. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Integrated Sensor Systems. (A) Base station to collect meteorological data and transfer data real-time via telemetric equipment (B) Sensor station to collect physiochemistry data and connect to base station (C) Example of sensor station box containing data logger and communication mechanism for real time data transmission to base station.

Hydrodynamic Modeling (Bowling Green State University)

In addition to Specialty Crew measurements above, the Program includes investment in a 3-D Hydrodynamic Modeling effort (Figure 8). Prototype 3-D models were completed for two Focal Projects: Brook Parks and St. Joseph Restoration. This means the key hydrologic and drainage features of the sites (e.g., streams, depressional ponds, tiles, natural flows, pumping) along with

boundary conditions were conceptually modeled and combined with bathymetry or elevation data to create a 3-D grid in which various conditions can be simulated. The 3-D Hydrodynamic Model Principal Investigator trained two graduate students in 3-D hydrodynamic modeling methods, communicated data needs with the other Specialty Crews, and advised on placement locations of wells for Base Crew groundwater sampling. Development of 3-D models for two Focal Projects; Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West, began in 2022. Continued improved communication between ODNR, Project partners, and the Monitoring Program will be important in receiving elevation and bathymetry data where available. In addition, the dialogue between the 3-D Hydrodynamic Model PI, Specialty Crews, and Base Crews will continue to support calibration and validation needs (i.e., which data base and Specialty Crews need to collect to calibrate the 3-D hydrodynamic model).

The 3-D Hydrodynamic Model PI secured supplemental Ohio Department of Higher Education funding to further expand modeling efforts. This study titled “Translating wetland monitoring to better restoration and management: development of a novel simulation-optimization tool for nutrient reduction wetlands” will use models to optimize wetland design, restoration, and operation ideas/strategies for nutrient reduction. The new grant supports one post-doc researcher and one to two undergraduate students across two years and will leverage two H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Projects.

Figure 8. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program 3-D Hydrodynamic Model Example. Example outputs of a 3-D hydrodynamic model built using the Hydrogeosphere framework depicting simulated water depth at the Brooks Park Wetland Creation & Water Quality Initiative in Fairfield Count, OH adjacent to Buckeye Lake. These figures show how the created wetland pools respond to different hydrologic and boundary conditions: (A) inflow from Murphy’s run and outflow to Buckeye Lake during normal condition and (B) dominant inflow from Buckeye Lake during a wet and high lake-level condition.

Sediment-Scale Measurements (Kent State University and Wright State University)

The Sediment-Scale Specialty Crew conducts sampling and incubations to measure the mechanisms and rates of nutrient exchange between sediments and surface waters (Figure 9). In

2022, 48 intact sediment cores were collected for nutrient exchange incubations at three Focal Projects (Magee Marsh, Oakwoods East, Brooks Park). In addition, an *in-situ* field method was piloted at Magee Marsh, where the Crew deployed 27 stacked resin bag units (Figure 10). Finally, the Crews also began comparing commonly used sedimentation rate markers to identify best practices for measuring sediment accumulation rates at H2Ohio Projects.

A strength of 2022 was internal collaboration between Kent State University and Wright State University, and external collaboration with Tennessee Tech University to refine sediment core sampling design and intact core incubation protocols. Challenges of 2022 include limitation in total cores that can be collected and incomplete information about wetland zones to inform soil core collection. In 2023, sampling will be informed by preliminary hydrogeophysics data and closer collaboration with Vegetation and Base Crews. Data processing times should also improve in the future thanks to data processing infrastructure developed by a doctoral student at Kent State University who created an R script to convert nutrient data to calculate flux, based on a pre-existing template.

Figure 9. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rate Measurements Using Intact Cores. (A) collecting an intact sediment core for sediment-surface water nutrient exchange measurement incubation. (B) Intact sediment cores incubating in flow-through system (C) schematic of flow-through intact core incubation system.

Figure 10. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Sediment-Surface Water Nutrient Exchange Rate Measurements *in situ* Ion Exchange Resins Resin bag technique. (A) Illustration of how stacked resin bag cores containing mixed media ion exchange resins were deployed to measure sediment-surface water nutrient exchange. (B) resin bag core. (C) 1-m² grid at each core sampling location.

Data Management Infrastructure

The H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program collects a variety of data types through a range of sampling methods in H2Ohio Projects across Ohio (Appendix, Table A6). The Program’s diffuse and diverse data collection requires diligent data management that supports centralization and assures quality. The development of data management workflows for the H2Ohio WMP was primarily performed by the Chief Data Manager, with collaboration from the Department of Computer Sciences and Engineering (CSE) and the Translational Data Analytics Institute (TDAI) at Ohio State University, the Ohio Supercomputer (OSC), with contributions from the Research Coordinator and Monitoring Program staff. In 2022, several workflows were improved and implemented to verify data quality and improve efficiency of data collection and distribution for Base and Specialty Crews. The workflows described in more detail below were drafted and user-tested in 2021 with many successfully launched in 2022. In general, data management highlights include:

- Refined six data collection and sample tracking surveys for internal Program use in 2022.
- Tested two data collection surveys for external partner use.
- Initial electronic data collection surveys transferred from Esri ArcGIS Field Maps product to the Esri ArcGIS Survey123 application due to the preferred capabilities, based on preliminary 2021 feedback between Crews and Program Chief Data Manager.
- Developed automated workflows to transfer survey-collected field data daily to version-controlled repositories on the hosting service GitHub, and track data quality by flagging violations to quality criteria, revisions, and issue resolutions.
- Water, soil, vegetation, sensor, and hydrogeophysics tabular 2022 data stored on GitHub.
- Uploaded non-tabular drone data to the Ohio Supercomputer in 2022.

Electronic Data Collection Surveys

Electronic data collection forms (hereafter “surveys”) were developed for several data streams, including water and soil sample metadata, physicochemical measurements, vegetation community composition and biomass sample metadata, and sensor status tracking. The surveys were initially developed in the Esri ArcGIS Field Maps product, but ultimately transferred to the Esri ArcGIS Survey123 application due to the preferred capabilities that include extensive support for offline use. These electronic forms are bespoke data entry systems that support specific data types and data collection needs of each Crew. In 2022, the Program distributed tablets and GPS units to all Base Crews to allow for field and laboratory use of the surveys. Electronic data collection surveys achieve four programmatic data management goals:

1. Ensure thorough metadata documentation and unique sample identification and tracking.
2. Implement comprehensive quality assurance steps to reduce errors.
3. Increase efficiency by removing data transcription (in lieu of only analog data records).
4. Seamlessly centralize data storage from all Crews into one common repository.

In total, five surveys were released to Base Crews for use in: 1) Routine Monitoring of completed wetland Projects, 2) Site characterization and supplemental sampling at wetland

Projects in pre- or post-construction, 3) Logging of sensor status (e.g., deployment, calibration), 4) Tracking sample chain-of-custody, 5) Following hydrologic management actions in coastal wetland Projects (e.g., opening and closing of water level control structures). In addition, one survey was comprehensively developed and revised for the Vegetation Specialty Crew for the collection of community composition and biomass sample metadata. This survey was structured to substantially decrease frequency of typos, numerical errors, and time spent typing metadata while identifying vegetation taxa in the field. Two formal training sessions were offered internally to current and new WMP staff to ensure aptitude and effective use of the respective surveys. Over 90% of water, soil, biomass and samples and physicochemical measurements collected by the Program staff to date have been recorded via the surveys.

To fulfill the Program's demand for collaboration and guidance beyond the Base and Specialty Crews, two publicly available surveys were also developed in 2022 using Esri ArcGIS Survey123: 1) Site Characterization and Supplemental Sampling and 2) Management Actions Tracking. Both public surveys were revised and user-tested in 2022 and are on track to be launched widely to appropriate partners in 2023. The Program's primary objective for the publicly available surveys is to facilitate aggregation of all H2Ohio-related datasets by centralizing data collected at H2Ohio wetland Projects, facilitating data access, and sharing and employing consistent data quality criteria across Projects.

The Site Characterization and Supplemental Sampling survey allows Program partners and external researchers that collect data at H2Ohio wetland Projects to input sample metadata and physicochemical measurement data consistent with Program data collection procedures. The Management Actions Tracking survey is aimed at partners, collaborators, managers, or landowners responsible for water level and vegetation management, oversight of wetland design changes, or facilitation of community science initiatives. The survey is structured to record basic activity information (e.g., date/time, location, brief description) and provide the Program with a general sense of the ongoing management actions at the wetland Projects. All these activities directly or indirectly influence the Program's sampling decisions, and therefore tracking them is highly justified and valuable in the short and long term.

Centralized Data Storage

Tabular data generated by the Program have been stored in version-controlled online repositories within the hosting service GitHub. The repositories are dedicated exclusively to H2Ohio WMP data and managed within an organization account (@h2ohio-wmp) for quality checks and internal data sharing. In 2022, the Chief Data Manager developed automated workflows to transfer and backup survey-collected data to GitHub daily. An analogous workflow is in place to transfer data generated by the Sensor Specialty Crew (i.e., high-resolution data from telemetric sensor networks) to GitHub from the online dashboard service where it is temporarily stored (i.e., Ubidots). In the online repositories, the Chief Data Manager designed and implemented automated quality control Programs to check the data quality of water and soil sample metadata and physicochemical measurements based on Program-wide established quality standards. Similar automated quality checks are under development for additional data streams, and quality criteria for most water chemistry analyses and sensor data have already been determined. A

system for quality issue tracking is in place that alerts the Chief Data Manager when data are flagged for violating quality criteria and thoroughly documents issue resolution. In its entirety, this system automates data exports and quality control checks in near real-time from data collection.

Non-Tabular Data Management and Storage

Data generated by the Drone and Hydrogeophysics Specialty Crews are inherently different from the strictly tabular datasets derived from other Crews. These data are generally large in file size and stored in a variety of formats that can aggregate geospatial or multidimensional information. To accommodate these files, an academic account was established at OSC for the H2Ohio WMP with Dr. Kristen Fussell (LEARN representative) as the Principal Investigator. The Monitoring Program requested six terabytes (TB) of storage for this academic account to host non-tabular data and large files originating from the WMP. Both raw and processed drone imagery and mosaics are currently stored and organized in directories within this repository. Hydrogeophysics files, which include a combination of tabular and raster files, are temporarily stored in GitHub but will be moved to OSC in 2023.

PostgreSQL Database Development

After passing acceptance criteria, all tabular data will be ultimately stored in a custom-built PostgreSQL database also hosted at OSC. The development of the database infrastructure was done in collaboration with the Department of Computer Sciences & Engineering and TDAI at Ohio State University. A master's student advised by Dr. Srinivasan Parthasarathy developed computing code, established automations, and tested database connection hosted in a virtual machine at OSC. Weekly meetings were held between the Chief Data Manager, CSE and TDAI collaborators to communicate the Program's structure and needs, provide the information necessary for database development, build several iterations of a database schema, and progressively adjusting to the substantial workflow revisions in the first two years of data collection.

The collaboration with CSE and TDAI was temporarily paused mid-2022 due to the graduation of the master's student involved in the database development, a shift in data priorities for the Program, and anticipated budget constraints. Focus was redirected to the establishment of robust data collection and quality check systems, that precede the structure of the database. The database schema continued to be updated by the Chief Data Manager and it is currently in draft format while the development of the underlying data workflows is finalized. The Program plans to re-engage with CSE/TDAI collaborators in 2023 to aid in the implementation of a revised database schema.

Program Coordination

Training Materials and Documentation

To respond to the exponential growth in wetland restoration Projects and to address the challenge of integrating a Monitoring Program into researchers' academic schedules, the Program needed staff dedicated to technical support, partner relationship-building, and early monitoring efforts.

As of December 2022, there are two full-time Program support personnel. There are 11 Crew-level technical staff (nine are full-time and two are part-time; Appendix, Table A3). The Program Coordinator and Chief Data Manager created employee onboarding documents, guidance documents, and Program tracking tools to ensure standardized monitoring and efficient documentation among geographically diffuse Crews. In addition, training materials and Program guidance documents were drafted. For example, a “Field Visit Quick Guide” was compiled and sent to all Crews in September, it documents Program best practices and will contribute to a larger Program Operations Manual in 2023.

Communication Pathways

Two Program management tools were further implemented in 2022:

1. Smartsheet is a collaborative workflow software in which the Chief Data Manager and Program Research Coordinator have developed a series of field visit forms and other tracking documents to ensure diligent documentation of Program tasks and status of monitoring Projects.
2. Slack is an instant messaging Program in which the Chief Data Manager and Program Research Coordinator have organized communication around a diverse suite of topics and decisions facing the Monitoring Program.

In 2022, whole WMP researcher meetings (all PIs and staff) adjusted each quarter (from weekly, to bi-weekly, to monthly) to improve meeting efficiency and impact. Decision-making and topics covered during the 21 total hours of whole team research meetings included field season progress, annual workshop topics, sensor network plans, and specific Crew updates. In August, bi-weekly technical check-ins were implemented with the Monitoring Program Research Coordinator, Chief Data Manager, coordinators, and technicians to keep logistical tasks connected among Crews.

The Program continued weekly meetings of Core Program Leadership to address the administrative needs of the collaboration and monthly meetings of Monitoring Program Research Coordinator and ODNR-LEARN liaison to communicate Project-level updates. In addition, a workflow was between the Monitoring Program and ODNR Project Leads to clarify which geographic Base Crew is responsible for which ODNR’s Project Lead’s Project.

Opportunity and Outreach

Scientific Collaboration

The Program continued to engage in development and feedback for improvement in 2022. The Data Analysis Working Group functioned as an advisory group that provides advice on how to scale up and utilize Bayesian Network Modeling approaches for synthesizing Monitoring Program data. The Nutrient Budget Working Group is a small group of WMP researchers who discussed how sampling can be improved and informed by Project-level nutrient budget conceptual models. A small subset of Program researchers met to select tools for expansion of water level monitoring. In addition, The Program collaborated with Cleveland Water Alliance to deploy sensors at Magee Marsh. Supply chain issues hindered the Program’s ability to gather continuous data in 2022, therefore the loaned sensors allowed continued training of staff on

sensor assembly, configuration, and installation which led to important preliminary data collection.

Finally, Program researchers invited external researchers to discuss expertise related to sampling and potential for leveraging Projects for supplementary research including:

- Kevin Kratt (TetraTech) discussed wetland nutrient and sediment load reduction analysis.
- Jon Witter and Dan Mecklenburg (The Ohio State University) discussed 2-Stage Ditches.
- Justin Murdoc (Tennessee Technological University) discussed soil sampling strategies.
- Greg McCarthy (U.S. Department of Agriculture) discussed potential groundwater study.

Public and Professional Outreach

The annual public webinar hosted by Ohio Sea Grant and LEARN on October 12th, 2022, was attended virtually by 157 people and over 70 questions were pre-submitted. In conjunction with the public webinar, the H2Ohio WMP worked with Ohio Sea Grant to update a two-page [brochure](#). Program researchers presented 11 other talks and attended nine ribbon-cutting or outreach events, including sessions at International Association of Great Lakes Research’s State of Lake Erie Conference and the Joint Aquatic Science Meeting (Appendix, Table A7).

Leveraging Monitoring Efforts to Build Capacity

A strength of the Program is its ability to interface with other researchers, educators, and community scientists. While some of the following efforts are outside the scope of the Program’s core mandate and funding, the relationships built, funds leveraged, and scientific inquiry all feed back into strengthening the Program’s understanding of restored wetlands.

Supplemental Funding

- Ganming Liu (Bowling Green State University) received an Ohio Department of Higher Education Grant to expand 3-D hydrodynamic modeling at H2Ohio wetlands. (Contact: gliu@bgsu.edu)
- Janice Kerns (Ohio Department of Natural Resources), Lauren Kinsman-Costello (Kent State University) and Thomas Bridgeman (University of Toledo) received an US EPA Great Lakes Restoration Initiative Grant to enhance sensor network implementation and calibration at H2Ohio wetlands. (Contact: janice.kerns@dnr.ohio.gov)

Graduate Student Research (“*” indicates research conducted by part-time or full-time H2Ohio technical staff)

- Seyi Ogundeji*, advised by Richard Becker (University of Toledo) tested the efficacy of two different spectral imagery processing techniques with flights from H2Ohio-restored wetlands. (Contact: seyi.ogundeji@rockets.utoledo.edu)
- Mica Rumbach, advised by Kevin McCluney (Bowling Green State University) investigated how snails and crayfish alter primary producers and nutrient cycling at Oakwoods East, an early H2Ohio-restored wetland. (Contact: mrumbac@BGSU.edu)

- Michael Back*, advised by Lauren Kinsman-Costello (Kent State University) compares the feasibility of in-tact soil core incubation and *in-situ* resin bag deployments for measuring soil nutrient flux at Magee Marsh. (Contact: mback@kent.edu)
- Taylor Michael, advised by Lauren Kinsman-Costello (Kent State University) estimates waterfowl contribution to wetland nutrients at Magee Marsh. (Contact: tmichae9@kent.edu)
- Nana-Aboagye Otchere*, advised by Kennedy Doro (University of Toledo) examines the variation in subsurface flow of water through Fruth Nature Preserve, the first H2Ohio-restored wetland. (Contact: nana-Aboagye.otchere@rockets.utoledo.edu)
- Hannah LaPoint*, advised by Kennedy Doro (University of Toledo) assesses how substrate properties impact groundwater contributions at H2Ohio-restored wetlands and develops methods to image sub-bottom sediments in shallow water bodies using EMI and GPR at Magee Marsh. (Contact: hannah.lapoint@utoledo.edu)
- Ibrahim Mohammed, advised by Ganming Liu and Bob Midden (Bowling Green State University) simulates hydrological complexities of a H2Ohio-restored wetlands (Contact: mibrah@bgsu.edu)

Undergraduate Student Research

- Grace Watson*, advised by Lauren Kinsman-Costello and mentored by Mike Back (Kent State University) compared phosphorus storage in sediment and water among different vegetation patches at Magee Marsh.
- Emma Jackman, supervised by Helen Michaels, Lauren Brown, Ewan Isherwood (Bowling Green State University) examines if leaf nutrient content is a sufficient proxy measurement for whole plant nutrient content.
- Nicole Hildebrand, supervised by Helen Michaels, Kevin McCluney, Lauren Brown, and Ewan Isherwood (Bowling Green State University) examines competition between multiple wetland plants.
- Lucy Busselle, supervised by Bob Midden (Bowling Green State University) investigates spatial variable conditions at Oakwoods East and Oakwoods West to adequately estimate the project's effect on net nutrient export over time.

Community Science Partnerships

The Monitoring Program is actively engaged in making connections to various educational groups to empower community scientists. Successful interactions included ODNR's H2Ohio Students Take Action program and providing information to an H2Ohio Naturalist to assist local teachers in the use of [Chronolog](#) installations at Oakwoods East, Oakwoods West, and Brooks Park. In addition, the Program's first [Crowd Hydrology](#) staff gauge was installed at Sandusky River Headwaters Preserve; Crowd Hydrology data indicate water level change (>1-ft change back and forth) across a season (Figure 11). Observing water level is the first step in assessing change in water volume. Changes in water volume help estimate residence time, which affects nutrient processing. While staff gauges provide an important standardized measurement at a single point in a wetland pool, bathymetry (pool shape) along with higher temporal resolution and accurate water level logger measurements are needed to supplement this analog data.

Figure 11. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Crowd Hydrology Citizen Science. (Left) Staff gauge installed in partnership with the national citizen science Crowd Hydrology program (crowdhydrology.com) (Right) Gauge Height at Sandusky River Headwaters, downloaded from Crowdhydrology.com.

Upcoming H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Goals and Objectives

Overarching Goals

In 2023, the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program will continue work toward the goal of assessing the nutrient removal function, either directly or by evidence-based proxy, of ODNR-implemented H2Ohio wetland Projects and assessing Program-wide effectiveness of wetland implementation. All Monitoring Program activities will continue to be shaped by the guiding principles of 1) responsible, open, and sound science, 2) a community of researchers, professionals, and partners, 3) learning by doing in an adaptive framework, 4) focus on wetland function, and 5) building a foundation for long-term monitoring.

As the number of completed wetland projects expands beyond the Monitoring Program's capacity to directly monitor each Project, Program researchers will continue to refine sampling designs in select, representative Projects. Program staff will lead centralization of documented standard operating procedures and quality assurance criteria to ensure credibility and usefulness of datasets and other products. 2022 represented the Program's first year of "routine monitoring" in completed Projects. In 2023 and in future years, Program researchers will collect data as new restoration Projects are completed and as completed Projects develop ecologically. In 2023, data collected in 2022 will be curated, collated, checked for accuracy and errors, and ultimately summarized as the first year of baseline data for completed Projects. Data summary, synthesis, and communication efforts will be supported through shifting some resources away from data collection toward data processing.

2023 Program Objectives

To achieve those Overarching Goals, the Wetland Monitoring Program will work toward completing the following Objectives and Tasks.

Data Processing and Presentation

- Complete curation of data and metadata that had been collected prior to automated survey implementation.
- Develop and distribute a dashboard for sharing provisional data with stakeholders.
- Compile examples of current data synthesis products from individual Crews to generate standard templates and guidance for data synthesis products.
- Produce data synthesis products, centrally by Program coordination staff and individually by Monitoring Program Crews at different institutions.
- Solicit input on draft data products from ODNR staff and project partners to ensure impactful communication of results.

Standardize Sampling and Protocol Documentation

- Continue standardization of sampling across institutions by compiling and documenting Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) currently used by individual crews into one Program-wide set of SOPs and policies.
 - Complete draft field sampling, lab analysis, and data management protocols.
 - Review draft protocols at internal H2Ohio Researcher meetings before the LEARN annual meeting.
- Draft training documents and certification process for app-based collection of field data.
- Draft instruction documents and distribute the link for the management action tracking public survey to partners at current routine monitoring Projects.
- Publish 2023 Monitoring Plan and Project Specific Monitoring Plans on Open Science Framework.

Expand Water Level Monitoring and Sample Transient Events

- Further expand water level monitoring across multiple Projects and increase spatial and temporal resolution within Projects.
 - Deploy staff gauges for standardized water level measurements at all Focal Projects, and at as many routinely monitored non-Focal Projects as possible.
 - Order and deploy lower cost water level loggers at all Focal Projects not currently slated for full sensor systems, and at as many routinely monitored non-Focal Projects as possible.
- Increase event-based sampling (i.e., post-storm, post-water level management action) to capture transient flooding and stormflow events.

Improve Coordination Among Monitoring Crews

- Improve inter-crew coordination to align sampling across specialty and base crews, confirm datasets align toward scientific analysis and data synthesis products.

- Require bi-weekly technical check-in meetings with Program technical staff with at least one member of each Base and Specialty Crews attending.
- Align drone flights and vegetations via shared calendar and immediate (< 2 week) dialogue between crews to discern vegetation patch locations.
- Automate alert system for respective Base Crew when Specialty Crew indicates field sampling plans on the Smartsheet form.

2023 Sampling Overview

- Continue six Focal Project sites (Brooks Park, Oakwoods West, Oakwoods East, Forder Bridge, St. Joesph Restoration, Magee Marsh) and add two new Focal sites (Burntwood-Langenkamp, Redhorse Bend)
- Sample or conduct initial information gathering at a total of ~72 Projects.
 - 11 Projects in Routine Monitoring Year 2.
 - 7 Projects in Routine Monitoring Year 1.
 - 21 Project in post-construction characterization (includes sampling).
 - 19 Projects in pre-construction characterization (likely includes sampling).
 - 14 Projects in initial inquiry (information-gathering but may not sample).

Appendix

Table A1. 2022 Monitored H2Ohio Wetland Projects. ODNR H2Ohio Initiative Projects monitored in 2022, restoration status, and monitoring phase. Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. Char = characterization; (Pre) = pre-construction; (Post) = post-construction.

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	Restoration Phase		Monitoring Phase		
			In Progress	Complete	Char. (Pre)	Char. (Post)	Routine
Northwest Inland	BRIC	Bright Wetland	•		•		
	FORB	Forder Bridge		•			•
	MONW	Montpelier Wetland	•		•		
	OAKE	Oakwoods East		•			•
	OAKW	Oakwoods West		•			•
	OOPR	Oak Openings Preserve		•			•
	OTSS	Otsego Schools	•		•		
	SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence		•			•
	SJRE	St. Joseph Restoration		•			•
	VANO	Van Order		•			•
	WEIP	Weisgerber-Pohlman		•			•
Northcentral	ANDW	Andreoff Wetland		•		•	
	BUEF	Buehler Farms		•		•	
	CMBC	Clary-Boulee-McDonald		•	•		
	FRUW	Fruth Wetland		•			•
	REDB	Redhorse Bend		•			•
	SPRM	Springville Marsh		•		•	
	SRHE	Sandusky River Headwaters		•			•
	SUGB	Sugarcamp 7		•		•	
	UPPB	Upper Blanchard		•		•	
Northeast	CHIL	Chippewa Lake	•		•		
	TRUC	Trumbull Creek		•		•	
Northwest Coastal	BOHM	Bohling Marsh		•			•
	DARR	Darby Refuge		•			•
	DUCO	Duck and Otter	•		•		
	MAGM	Magee Marsh		•			•
	MAUB	Maumee Bay State Park		•		•	
	NORR	North Ridge		•			•
	OTTN	Ottawa NWR		•			•
Southwest & Central	BROP	Brooks Park		•			•
	BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp		•			•
	COLW	Coldwater Wetland	•		•		
	GORF	Gorman Farm	•		•		
	HELB	Hellbranch Meadows	•		•		
	INDC	Indian Creek	•		•		
	MERW	Mercer Wetland	•		•		
	ODOW	O'Donnell Wetland	•		•		
	RAIR	Rainbow Run	•		•		
	SPES	Spencerville Stormwater	•		•		
	SPRC	Springcreek Confluence		•			•
	SPRR	Spring Run	•		•		
	STMA	St. Mary's	•		•		
	TIPC	Tipp City		•		•	
	WALC	Walnut Creek	•		•		
	WESW	Westchester Wetland	•		•		

Table A2. 2022 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Routinely Monitored Project Attributes. Key attributes of 19 ODNR-implemented H2Ohio wetland restoration Projects monitored by the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program in 2022. For more details regarding attributes and monitoring of specific Projects, 2022 Project Specific Monitoring Plans are available upon request. Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. WLC = presence/absence of water level control structures; Tile = presence/absence of tile drain inputs; Year = year Project construction was completed.

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	Hydrologic Structure Type and Attributes					Other Project Information					
			Isolated Depressional	Floodplain	Flow-through	Coastal	WLC	Tile	Land Use Type	County	Acres	Year	
Northwest Inland	FORB	Forder Bridge	●	●	●			●	Conservancy	Paulding	5	2021	
	OAKE	Oakwoods East	●					●	County Park	Hancock	30	2021	
	OAKW	Oakwoods West	●	●			●		County Park	Hancock	20	2021	
	OOPR	Oak Openings	●						Metropark	Lucas	22	2022	
	SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence	●	●					Conservancy	Williams	31	2021	
	SJRE	St. Joseph Restoration	●	●	●			●	Conservancy	Williams	33	2021	
	VANO	Van Order	●						State Forest	Henry	5	2022	
North Central	WEIP	Weisgerber-Pohlman	●	●					Conservancy	Williams	70	2021	
	FRUW	Fruth Wetland	●					●	County Park	Seneca	10	2021	
	REDB	Redhorse Bend	●	●					County Park	Sandusky	25	2021	
	SPRM	Springville Marsh	●	●					County Park	Crawford	7	2021	
Northwest Coastal	BOHM	Bohling Marsh			N/A				Private Individual	Ottawa	55	2021	
	DARR	Darby Refuge					●	●	Federal Wildlife Refuge	Ottawa	352	2021	
	MAGM	Magee Marsh					●	●	State Wildlife Area	Ottawa	173	2021	
	NORR	North Ridge		●	●			●	●	Private Individual	Ottawa	23	2021
	OTTN	Ottawa NWR					●	●	Federal Wildlife Refuge	Lucas	586	2021	
Southwest & Central	BROP	Brooks Park			●			●	State Park	Fairfield	5	2021	
	BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp			●			●	County Park	Mercer	27	2022	
	SPRC	Springcreek Confluence		●					County Park	Miami	25	2021	

Table A3. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Staff. All staff are full-time unless otherwise noted. Asterisks (*) indicate replacement for previous staff, all others were hired in 2022.

	Continued Staff	New Staff
Program Core	Raissa Mendonca (KSU) from Research Coordinator to Chief Data Manager	Olivia Johnson* (KSU; March 2022, Research Coordinator)
Northwest Inland		Genna Hunt (BGSU; August 2022, part-time field lead)
		Corbin Kohart* (BGSU; September 2022, full-time lab lead)
Northwest Coastal	Zachary Swan (UT) from Base Crew to Sensor Infrastructure Specialist	Amber Beecher* (UT; March 2022)
Northcentral	Jakob Boehler (HU; advisory support)	James Austin (HU; June 2022)
Southwest & Central	Justin Meyer (WSU Dayton Campus)	Morgan Jutte (WSU Lake Campus; June 2022)
Northeast	Mike Back (KSU; part-time field lead)	
Drone		Amar Kolapkar (UT; September 2022)
Vegetation	Lauren Brown (BGSU)	
	Ewan Isherwood (BGSU)	
Hydrogeophysics	Hannah LaPoint (UT)	

Table A4. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Sampling 2021 & 2022. Base Crew sampling accomplishments for 2021 and 2022 monitoring seasons, and approximate analysis status (% chemical analyses completed as of December 2022) for water and soil samples. Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. Number of samples collected \pm 10%; Percent samples analyzed \pm 20%; – Not yet complete or under monitoring; NA Not applicable.

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	2021		2022		% Analyzed	
			Water	Soil	Water	Soil	Water	Soil
Northwest Inland	BRIC	Bright Wetland	–	–	6	25	100%	100%
	FORB	Forder Bridge	34	0	118	62	100%	100%
	MONW	Montpellier Wetland	–	–	0	33	0%	100%
	OAKE	Oakwoods East	50	1	117	94	98%	100%
	OAKW	Oakwoods West	41	0	116	63	98%	100%
	OOPR	Oak Openings Preserve	12	27	58	25	100%	63%
	OTSS	Otsego Schools	–	–	3	9	100%	100%
	SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence	15	14	39	15	100%	100%
	SJRE	St. Joseph Restoration	66	26	121	80	100%	100%
	VANO	Van Order	8	44	35	29	100%	62%
	WEIP	Weisgerber-Pohlman	3	22	28	21	61%	100%
Northcentral	ANDW	Andreoff Wetland	–	–	1	0	100%	NA
	BUEF	Buehler Farms	–	–	1	0	0%	NA
	CBMC	Clary-Boulee-McDonald	–	–	3	0	100%	NA
	FRUW	Fruth Wetland	25	0	18	12	33%	50%
	REDB	Redhorse Bend	36	0	28	11	45%	82%
	SPRM	Springville Marsh	–	–	1	0	100%	NA
	SRHE	Sandusky River Headwaters	21	0	21	6	45%	0%
	SUGB	Sugarcamp 7	–	–	2	0	100%	NA
	UPPB	Upper Blanchard	–	–	1	0	100%	NA
Northeast	CHIL	Chippewa Lake	–	–	8	6	100%	0%
	TRUC	Trumbull Creek	–	–	17	6	100%	0%

Table A4, continued

Base Crew	Project Code	Project Name	2021		2022		% Analyzed	
			Water	Soil	Water	Soil	Water	Soil
Northwest Coastal	BOHM	Bohling Marsh	3	0	9	0	42%	NA
	DARR	Darby Refuge	17	4	57	12	65%	100%
	DUCO	Duck & Otter Creek	–	–	22	0	100%	NA
	LITP	Little Portage	7	4	–	–	100%	0%
	MAGM	Magee Marsh	13	3	129	41	37%	30%
	MAUB	Maumee Bay State Park	6	2	4	1	0%	100%
	MOXW	Moxley Wetland	6	4	–	–	100%	0%
	NORR	North Ridge	11	5	52	11	49%	81%
	OTTN	Ottawa NWR	21	2	47	8	43%	100%
Southwest & Central	BAUD	Baughman Ditch	0	6	–	–	NA	100%
	BROP	Brooks Park	50	10	106	24	100%	100%
	BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp	4	9	120	4	85%	100%
	COLW	Coldwater Wetland	–	–	0	5	NA	100%
	GORF	Gorman Farm	–	–	0	3	NA	100%
	HELB	Hellbranch Meadows	–	–	0	3	NA	100%
	INDC	Indian Creek	–	–	1	3	100%	100%
	MERW	Mercer Wetland	0	3	0	14	NA	100%
	ODOW	O'Donnell Wetland	–	–	2	4	100%	100%
	RAIR	Rainbow Run	–	–	1	3	100%	100%
	SPES	Spencerville Stormwater	–	–	0	3	NA	100%
	SPRC	Springcreek Confluence	40	5	60	3	5%	100%
	SPRR	Spring Run	–	–	2	8	100%	100%
	STMA	St. Mary's	–	–	1	4	100%	100%
	TIPC	Tipp City	0	6	4	4	100%	90%
	WALC	Walnut Creek	–	–	1	4	100%	100%
WESW	Westchester Wetland	–	–	0	2	NA	100%	

Table A5. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Specialty Data Collection 2022. Overview of specialty data collection and processed data products produced in 2022 by H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Specialty Crews. Intensively monitored focal projects are indicated in bold. GPR = Ground-penetrating radar; EC = Electrical conductivity; ERT = Electrical Resistivity Tomography. Filled circles indicate completed tasks, open circles indicate tasks in progress.

Project Code	Project Name	Aerial Imagery			Vegetation			Hydrogeophysics			Sediment	
		Drone Flight	Orthomosaic	Digital Elevation Models	Object-based Vegetation Classifications	Community Ground Truthing	Above-ground Biomass	Below-ground Biomass	GPR, EC, & ERT	Soil Samples	Piezometers	In-tact Core
BROP	Brooks Park	●	●	●	●	●	●		●	●		●
BWLK	Burntwood-Langenkamp	●	●	●								
FORB	Forder Bridge	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●		
FRUW	Fruth Wetland	●	●	●		●	●		●	●	○	
MAGM	Magee Marsh											● ●
NORR	North Ridge					●	●					
OAKE	Oakwoods East	●	●	●		●	●	●				●
OAKW	Oakwoods West	●	●	●	●	●	●	●				
OTTN	Ottawa NWR					●	●					
REDB	Redhorse Bend	●	●	●		●	●					
SJCO	St. Joseph Confluence	●	●	●		●	●					
SJRE	St. Joseph Restoration	●	●	●		●	●	●	●		○	
SRHE	Sandusky River Headwaters	●	●	●		●	●					

Table A6. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Dataset Management. Overview of data types collected by the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program and current status of custom-built infrastructure to support semi-automated quality assurance and quality control, long-term data storage, and sharing capabilities.

Data Type	Survey	2022 Status	Next Steps	Current storage	Planned storage
Water/soil sample metadata	Yes	Automated export/backup Quality criteria established Automated quality checks	Refine quality criteria Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database
Physicochemical measurements	Yes	Automated export/backup Quality criteria established Automated quality checks	Refine quality criteria Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database
Biomass sample metadata	Yes	Automated export/backup Quality criteria to be drafted	Establish quality criteria Setup automated quality checks Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database
Community composition metadata	Yes	Automated export/backup Quality criteria to be drafted	Establish quality criteria Setup automated quality checks Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database
Hydrogeophysics datasets	NA	Manual export/backup Quality criteria to be drafted	Establish quality criteria Setup automated quality checks Transfer data to OSC	GitHub	OSC
Raw and processed drone imagery	NA	Manual export/backup Quality criteria to be drafted	Establish quality criteria Setup manual quality checks	OSC	OSC
Sensor network datasets	NA	Automated export/backup Quality criteria drafted	Finalize quality criteria Setup automated quality checks Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database
Sensor status log	Yes	Automated workflows and dashboard development	Develop dashboard for data visualization and query	GitHub	GitHub, Dashboard
Sample chain-of-custody	<i>In revision</i>	Automated workflows and dashboard development	Develop dashboard for data visualization and query	GitHub	GitHub, Dashboard
Management actions	Yes	Automated workflows development	Establish alert system for Crews Automate data exports for long-term documentation	GitHub	GitHub, Dashboard
Coastal hydrologic management	Yes	Alert system for Crews Automated workflows development	Automate data exports for long-term documentation	GitHub	GitHub, Dashboard
External partner	Yes	Automated workflow development	Establish quality criteria Setup automated quality checks Revise database schema	GitHub	PostgreSQL Database

Table A7. 2022 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Select Meetings and Public Relations Activities.

February	Lauren Kinsman-Costello, Janice Kerns presented at the H2Ohio Director's meeting.
	Janice Kerns presented “H2Ohio Wetland Restoration and Monitoring Project” to the Great Lakes Coastal Assembly.
March	H2Ohio WMP Group chaired a session “Designing and evaluating wetlands to optimize environmental and ecological benefits” at State of the Lake Conference.
April	Ribbon Cutting and Earth Day ceremony at Oak Openings Preserve Project site. The Directors of ODNR, OEPA, ODA, and the Lake Erie Commission attended.
	Ribbon Cutting ceremony held at Indian Creek Project site, partnership established between the WSU Base Crew and the Miami Conservancy District.
May	Biggest Week in American Birding group toured Magee Marsh and learned about the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program from Tom Bridgeman.
	H2Ohio WMP Research Group members organized “Designing and Implementing Effective Long-Term Wetland Monitoring” session at the Joint Aquatic Sciences Meeting. The session included a panel with experts across multiple geographic regions and institutions. Researcher presentations included:
	“Designing and Implementing Long-Term Wetland Monitoring” by Silvia Newell.
	“Establishing a Flexible but Robust Framework to Assess Nutrient Removal in Diverse Wetland Restorations” by Lauren Kinsman-Costello.
“Strategies and challenges in the development of a data infrastructure for heterogeneous wetland monitoring data” by Raissa Mendonca.	
“Monitoring Total Above and Belowground Plant Nutrient Content Across Multiple Wetlands” by Lauren Brown.	
June	Chris Winslow provided H2Ohio WMP updates during “Forecast for Harmful Algal Blooms in Lake Erie 2022” in a live web event for NOAA’s annual HABs Forecast.
August	Lauren Kinsman-Costello presented to coastal decision makers, community planners, development professionals during Ohio Sea Grant Stone Lab’s Decision Maker’s Day.
	Lauren Kinsman-Costello presented to major press outlets such as the Toledo Blade and Cleveland Plain Dealer and Lake Erie Charter Boat Captains during Ohio Sea Grant and Stone Lab’s Lake Erie Outdoor and Science Writers Conference.
	Wright State and Heidelberg full-time technicians attended a tour of Burntwood-Langenkamp Project site hosted by Mercer Soil & Water Conservation District.
September	Lauren Kinsman-Costello and Bob Midden attended an Oakwoods Nature Preserve trail ribbon cutting event along with ODNR Director Mertz and Eric Saas, Hancock Park District partners, and public stakeholders.
October	Lauren Brown presented "Designing methods for monitoring total above and belowground plant nutrient content across multiple wetlands" during the weekly Research in Progress seminar for the Biological Sciences Department at BGSU.
	Stephen Jacquemin and Morgan Grunden met with ODNR Director Mertz, Eric Saas, and Governor DeWine at Burntwood-Langenkamp Project site and provided information on efforts to improve water quality in Grand Lake St. Marys.
	2022 Public Webinar
	Lauren Kinsman-Costello and Olivia Johnson participated in an International Joint Commission Great Lakes Citizen Science workshop to share perspective based on early wetland Monitoring Program experience.
November	Michael Back and Raissa Mendonca visited Fosters Run Project site with project partners along with Senator Dolan, ODNR Director Mertz, and Eric Saas.

Figure A1. H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program: ODNR-LEARN Coordination Workflows. Workflows used by the Ohio Department of Natural Resources (ODNR, left) and researchers from the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network (LEARN, right) in the H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program to document and manage the implementation and monitoring of H2Ohio wetland Projects.

Figure A2. 2022 and 2023 H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program Focal Projects. Focal Projects are wetland restoration projects implemented by the ODNR through the H2Ohio Water Quality Initiative selected for intensive, high-frequency monitoring in 2022 by the Lake Erie and Aquatic Research Network’s H2Ohio Wetland Monitoring Program. Six Focal Projects (MAGM, SJRE, FORB, OAKE, OAKW, BROP) were selected from 45 wetland Projects to represent major "types" of wetland restoration approaches in 2022. Two additional Projects were chosen as Focal Projects (REDB, BWLK) to start in 2023. REDB = Redhorse Bend; MAGM = Magee Marsh; SJRE = St. Joseph River Restoration; FORB = Forder Bridge; OAKE/OAKW = Oakwoods East, Oakwoods West; BWLK = Burntwood Langenkamp; BROP = Brooks Park.